

IMPLEMENTATION OF NORMATIVE LEGAL ACTS OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION. This article provides information on the implementation of normative legal acts of foreign countries in the development of preschool education and the stages of systematic organization of preschool education in foreign countries.

Keywords: implementation, preschool education, preschool organization, innovation, incorporation, transformation.

Introduction. The introduction of effective mechanisms for managing the public education system is the most important condition for raising the growing younger generation to a qualitatively new level of spiritual, moral and intellectual development, and also contributes to the application of innovative forms and methods of education in the educational process. The conditions that have arisen at the moment in our country necessitate a revision of the form, content of professional development and mechanisms for its implementation and the introduction of appropriate changes to this process. In particular, these days there was a need to improve the content and forms of professional development of their educators in order to carry out measures aimed at improving the system of preschool education. Program decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016 PF-5198 "on measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021"PQ-2707", decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2017"on measures to radically improve the management of the preschool education system "PF-5198", decree of September 9, 2017 " on, also, the introduction in practice of the state educational program of the preschool educational

institution “state requirements for the development of children of the first and preschool age” No. 1 mh of June 18, 2018 and “first step” of the Ministry of preschool education, on the basis of which it provides for improving the content of the processes of professional development The working curriculum of the module” modern approaches in preschool education " is compiled on the basis of the educational program of the course for professional development of Educators of preschool educational institutions, which reveals the content and essence of modern approaches and innovations, integrations in education to educators of 7 institutions of preschool education. Today, the tasks of obtaining a template from foreign experience, introducing it in practice with a creative approach, developing normative documents, educational literature, educational methodological complexes in accordance with the requirements of the time, the formation of knowledge and skills in the field of modern management and pedagogical technologies in the heads and specialists of preschool educational institutions on the basis of advanced Therefore, decrees and decisions were made to radically improve the system of preschool education in our country. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016 no PQ-2707 "on measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 20172021"on choratadbirs of radical improvement of the system of preschool education "dated September 9, 2017 no PQ-3261"on measures to radically improve the management of the preschool education system "dated September 30, 2017 PF-5198sonli it is from the sentence. We will consider the activities of the preschool education system in foreign countries on the example of a number of countries.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. Implementations - (in English “implementation, implementation, practical implementation”) is a specific way of implementing international obligations in reality on an internal scale, as well as introducing the norms of international law into the system of national law. The main requirement for implementation is strict adherence to the goals and content of the international structure. The methods of implementation are as follows: -

incorporation; -transformation; -general, separate or special link. After the denial, the norms of international law are repeated literally in the laws of the state, which carry out without any changes. In the process of transformation, a certain processing of the norms of the corresponding international treaty occurs when they are transferred to national legislation (usually this occurs due to the need to take into account national legal traditions and standards of legal techniques). In a general, private or special link, the norms of international law are not directly included in the text of the law, they are only mentioned. Thus, when carried out by reference, the application of the national legal norm becomes impossible without a direct reference to the original source - the text of the corresponding international treaty. International treaties ratified in a number of states automatically become part of national legislation. Thus, in accordance with the Constitution of the Russian Federation (Part 4 of Article 15), generally recognized principles and norms of international law in the Russian Federation and international treaties of the Russian Federation are an integral part of its legal system. If the International Treaty of the Russian Federation establishes rules that are different from those provided for by law, the rules of the international treaty apply. Japan is a very fast-growing state, which is largely due to the hard work and businesslike nature of the Japanese. The pursuit of all the innovations and ascents in the world, the use of the latest achievements and their further development - this has become the long-standing national habits of the Japanese people. In Japan, for a very long time, the most important place is occupied by the policy of applying science and techniques that take advantage of the mental capabilities of the people. Preschool education is given a lot of attention in Japan, because psychologists say that under the age of 7, a person absorbs 70% of knowledge, and the remaining 30% throughout his life. Preschool usually begins with the family. For Japanese women, motherhood comes first. Many Japanese women say that raising a child is the goals of their lives. The Japanese are in favor of the early maturity of the child. Emphasizes the various problems of upbringing at different ages. For example, at 1 year old – to instill a sense of self –

confidence, at 2 years old – to show Practical Art manual labor, at 3 years old – to educate a sense of duty, at 4 years old – to teach to distinguish between good and evil, at 5 years old-to educate leadership traits, to teach independence, to draw up plans and fulfill them. Children and girls are brought up differently. The son is treated as the future support of the family and taught to overcome difficulties. And girls are prepared for housework. In Japanese kindergartens, children are divided into small groups of 8 people – “Han”. These children are allocated “their place of work” in the kindergarten, they choose a name for their mistress. Thus, from the smallest age, they teach to work in a team. Each child in this group should have their place in the group. Such hanlar 22 will also be used at the next educational stage. In high school, Han are not permanent, they are changed every 5 months in order to get used to new conditions faster. Children aged 3-5 years are admitted to Japanese kindergartens. The purpose of kindergartens is to develop the mental and physical abilities of children, to educate the skills of independence and internal order, to teach how to properly react to the phenomena of society. Also, much attention is paid to teaching oral speech, the correct application of words. Interest in the creative characteristics of a person is aroused, such as fairy tales, books, music, sports games, painting. Currently, 60% of children are involved in preschool institutions. In order to switch to early admission to primary education, it is planned to involve all children aged 4-5 years in kindergarten. Kindergarten is the 1st stage of the system of formation of a citizen of the motherland in Japan. Particular attention is paid to the formation of skills of independent activity, collective consciousness, social responsibility. The main task of the kindergarten is to prepare the child for school. Classes in painting, music, rhythmic, physical education are held here. Individuality, no matter how good it is, does not attract children, is not accepted by the children's team. Primary education is called "syogakko". The system of continuing education, schools are divided as follows:

1. Primary School - 6 years.
2. High School-3 years.

3. High School-3 years.

The Federal Republic of Germany consists of 16 independent federal lands (regions), each with an educational system that varies according to its form. Educational institutions are mainly state-owned, for which there are government directives that belong to the educational program. The rights of the Federal government are limited in the adoption of basic laws, including in matters of financing. The following can be said about the costs of education: - not a single Federal land for study in state secondary, professional educational institutions gives students from home to school on all Federal lands, buses that transport students from school to home at their own expense; - almost all students are given textbooks and manuals for a small part of their value; - according to the existing federal

The Republic of South Korea attracts the attention of many researchers, the reason is that this state is one of the unique States of the Asia –Pacific region, which has acquired the achievements of post-industrial civilization. Koreans believe that the main task that must be fulfilled is the preservation of their traditional culture, the desire to connect political and socioeconomic reforms with their cultural and political identity, traditional values and orientations of the East. The 25 education system of this state is recognized as the “most effective” within industrialized countries, according to the conclusion of Unicef experts. One of the most important achievements of 212 Canadians is their education system. The quality of education in advanced universities and colleges is very high, and Canadian diplomas are recognized all over the world. In the international ranking, Canadian education is second only to the United States. Peculiarities are visible in the curriculum of different provinces of Canada. For example, preparation for school in a preschool institution in Quebec, Ontario, Manitob is 2 years, from 4 to 6 years, in Albert and British Columbia-1 year. The school year begins in the first week of September and ends in the last week of June. The average duration of education in Canadian schools is 12 years. Children from 6-7 years old begin to attend elementary school and study in it for 6 years. Studies in the elementary schools of Manitob and Ontario last 2

years longer than in other provinces. From the age of 12, children move to high school and study until the age of 16-18. Preschool education (MT) in Belgium lasts from 2.5 to 6 years. When they reach the age of 2.5, children are given to a preschool institution, due to which the number of children in the group changes throughout the year. The main goal of preschool groups is: the development of cognitive, cognitive (cognitive), communicative and creative abilities of children. Classes are conducted in the form of a game. Although preschool education is not included in the compulsory education program, in Belgium, up to about 90% of children participate in it. In most cases, preschool institutions will be integrated into primary schools. Children enter the first grade of elementary school when they reach the age of 6. Children between the ages of 6 and 11 are involved in French primary education schools. Primary school is free and compulsory. Its function is to provide reading, writing and computing skills. Training sessions will last from 9 am to 12 pm and from 14 am to 4 pm for 5 hours. School meals are paid, but at very reduced prices. Study in elementary grades is 5 years and is carried out in three stages:

1. Preparatory stage;

2. Elementary course (this stage lasts two years);

3. Deepened stage. - The structure of the educational system in the United States is as follows: preschool institutions where children are brought up from 3 to 5 years old; primary schools from 28 to 8 grades (in such schools they study from 6 to 13 years old);

- 9 - 12 - secondary schools consisting of classes (these schools are taught by children under 1417 years of age). It consists of the lower and upper stage. The next stage of education in the United States is higher education, it is colleges that are taught for 2 or 4 years, as well as dorilfununlar. Compulsory education in the USA is valid until the age of 16. Educational institutions in this country can be at the disposal of State, collective, private and religious institutions. In America, mothers are engaged in the upbringing of children under 3 years old, but they were not given any benefits. And from the age of 5, Education Begins in the so-called "Kinder

garde" training institutions. Primary school covers children from 6 to 13-15 years old. It is in elementary schools that the tasks of general literacy and vocational guidance are solved. Moving from class to class depends on the degree of assimilation of the student.

Conclusion. In place of the conclusion, it can be said that in the process of implication, the practical fulfillment of international obligations at the domestic level by converting the norms of international law into national laws and underground acts is systematically carried out in a number of states. In doing so, international treaties ratified in a number of states are automatically becoming part of national legislation. This creates broad conditions for the application of these in practice in the exchange of international experience in reforming the educational process of bari and adapting them in a cross-state context.

List of literature

1. Mirziyayev Sh.M. We will jointly build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017. - 28 b.
2. Mirziyayev Sh.M. " We will continue our path of national development with determination and take it to a new level, " the works of the President. Volume 2 /422- page T.: Uzbekistan, 2018.
3. Mirziyayev Sh.M. Tankidiy taxlil, Kat'iy discipline and personal responsibility- should be a daily procedure of each person's activity. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017. - 104 b.
4. Base program "kid", developers: S.Mirdjalilova, M.Rasuleva and hats. "Enlightenment-reinforcer" T., 2010 y.
5. Vakhidav M.. "Children's psychology" Tashkent. 1992.
6. Vahidav M.V. Psychology of preschool education. T., "Teacher", 1994
7. Davletshin M.G. and others. Age periods and pedagogical technology. T., 2004
8. Tairovna, Z. N. (2022). The Role of Didactic Tools in the Mathematical Development of Children. Spanish Journal of Society and Sustainability, 3, 39-40.

9. Махмудова, Д. М. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА КАТТА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАРНИ КИТОБХОНЛИККА ТАЙЁРЛАШ МЕТОДЛАРИ. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 1(6), 274-278.
10. Gafbullaeva M., D.Gaybullaeva, upbringing of children aged one to three years, T., Science publishing house, 2006.